

Effects of Catalyst Variation on Biodiesel Yield

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ABSTRACT

The type, purity and amount of catalyst used affect the conversion efficiency of the transesterification process of converting oil to biodiesel. In this study, the effect of alkali and acid catalysts variation was examined on biodiesel yield. Sodium hydroxide at different concentration of 0.6-1.6% to unused oil was used as a catalyst for transesterifying unused oil to biodiesel. The optimum biodiesel yield was achieved using 1.4 wt. % of NaOH to oil weight, which produced an 88.0% yield of transparent methyl ester. Similarly, HCl was used at different concentration (0.8-1.8% to oil weight) to catalyse the transesterification process of used oil to biodiesel because the performance of the acid catalyst (HCl) is not strongly affected by the free fatty acid. Hydrochloric acid at a concentration of 1.6% to the oil weight brings about optimum yield of biodiesel (60%) from used frying oil. The biodiesel yield gradually increases as the concentration of the catalyst increases up to 1.6% to the oil weight, further increase in the concentration of the catalyst beyond this point results in the formation of soap and gel which significantly reduces the biodiesel yield.

Keyword: Biodiesel, Catalyst, Methyl ester, Transesterification, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

Biodiesel has been defined an alternative to petroleum based diesel made from renewable resources such as vegetable oils and animal fats [1]. It contains no sulphur and does not contribute to green house effect as they have closed carbon cycle [2] [3] [4] cited by [5]. The main conversion process is transesterification. Transesterification process is the reaction of a triglyceride (fat/oil) with an alcohol to form esters and glycerol [6] [7].

The process is aided by a catalyst such as potassium hydroxide (KOH), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) etc [8] [9].

For base-catalysed transesterification process, any strong base can be used to deprotonate the alcohol [10]. (e.g. NaOH, KOH, sodium methoxide etc.), but the sodium and potassium hydroxides are often used (Gutierrez et al., 2009) for its cost and high yield.

METHODOLOGY

Alkali-Catalysed Transesterification

Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) at different concentration of 0.6-1.6% to oil weight was mixed with methanol and the mixture was poured into the mixer and stirred at 200 rpm for 20 minutes to ensure that the catalyst dissolves completely and the resulting mixture sodium methoxide is homogeneous. The equation of the reaction is

The feedstock (palm olein vegetable oil) was pre-heated to a temperature of 120°C in the reactor to remove any water vapour and other volatile impurities. The oil was allowed to cool to

60°C which is below the evaporating temperature of methanol. Sodium methoxide produced was then poured to the pre-heated oil in the reactor at a molar ratio of 6:1 (sodium methoxide in excess) and stirred rigorously at 200 rpm for 2 hours at a temperature of 60°C and ambient pressure after which the mixture was discharge through a funnel and allowed to settle for 24 hours to enhance effective separation. A successful transesterification reaction produces two liquid phases: esters and crude glycerol (Dermibas, 2005). After 24 hours, it was discovered that the product formed separated into two layers with the lighter methyl ester (biodiesel) at the top and glycerol at the bottom. The by-product (glycerol) was found to be heavier than biodiesel (i.e has higher density than the biodiesel formed), so biodiesel was carefully decanted. The crude biodiesel obtained contains some impurities which were separated by purification via methyl ester wash followed by drying process.

Acid Catalysed Transesterification

For this transesterification reaction, HCl is used as a catalyst because the performance of the acid catalyst (HCl) is not strongly affected by the presence of free fatty acids in the feedstock. The used frying oil was pre-heated to a temperature of 120°C, in order to remove trapped water molecules in the oil and then allowed to cool to 60°C. The acid catalyst (HCl) at a concentration of 0.8-1.8% of the weight of oil, was mixed with methanol to form methanolic HCl and the mixture was carefully poured into the used frying oil in the mixer at a molar ratio of 8:1 (methanolic HCl in excess) and stirred at 200 rpm for 8 hours after which it was discharged into a funnel and allowed to settle for 24 hours. After 24 hours, it was discovered

that the product formed separated into two layers with the lighter biodiesel at the top and denser glycerol at the bottom.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Varying Amount of Alkali- Catalyst (NaOH) on Biodiesel Yield

The effect of varying the amount of alkali- catalyst was studied for palm olein vegetable oil. Production of biodiesel was done with the catalyst (NaOH) in different amounts (wt. %) to the palm olein oil weight. Catalyst amount was varied in the range of 0.6-1.6 wt. % to oil for six different values (0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, and 1.6 wt. % of unused oil weight). The effect of the catalyst amount on yield is shown figure 1.0

Figure 1.0: Biodiesel yield With Different Alkali-Catalyst Amount (NaOH) Dissolved in Methanol

Catalyst amount was varied in the range 0.6-1.6 wt. % of NaOH to oil. The excess addition of NaOH increased the yield. The optimum biodiesel yield was achieved using 1.4 wt. % of NaOH to oil, which produced an 88.0% yield of transparent ester. NaOH greater than 1.4 wt. % to oil produced a smaller ester yield, because of the presence of soap and gel formation which prevents ester layer separation. This is similar to the result Ma and Hanna, 1998 [13] obtained when catalyst amount was varied in the range 0.2-1.5 wt. % of KOH.

Effect of Varying Amount of Acid-Catalyst (HCl) on Biodiesel Yield

The effect of varying the amount of acid-catalyst on biodiesel produced from used frying oil was also studied. Production of biodiesel was done with different amount of catalyst (HCl) dissolved in methanol. Catalyst amount was varied in the range of 0.8-1.8 wt. % to oil for six different values (0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6 and 1.8 wt. % of HCl). The effect of the catalyst amount on yield is shown figure 2.0

Figure 2.0: Biodiesel Yield with Different Acid-Catalyst Amount (HCl) Dissolved in Methanol

From Fig. 2.0, hydrochloric acid at a concentration of 1.6% to the oil weight brings about optimum yield of biodiesel (60%) from used frying oil. The biodiesel yield gradually increases as the concentration of the catalyst increases up to 1.6% to the oil weight, further increase in the concentration of the catalyst beyond this point results in the formation of soap and gel which significantly reduces the biodiesel yield.

Further more, the high free fatty of the feedstock (used frying oil) inhibits transesterification, this result in lower yield (60%) compared to the higher yield (80%) obtained from the transesterification of palm olein vegetable oil to biodiesel as shown in Fig. 2.0. This is the reason for increasing the catalyst concentration of HCl up to 1.6% to the weight of the oil.

CONCLUSION

The type, purity and amount of catalyst used affect the conversion efficiency of the transesterification process. Because of the presence of free fatty acid, acid catalysts are suitable for transesterifying used oil to biodiesel while alkali catalysts are often suitable for use in the conversion of pure vegetable oil to biodiesel. Impure catalyst tends to affect the rate and the conversion efficiency of the process. Increase in the amount of catalyst increases biodiesel yield but continual increase in catalyst amounts produced a smaller methyl ester yield, because of the presence of soaps which prevents ester layer separation.

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